

TRANSPORT RESEARCH DATA CULTURE & SURVEY HIGHLIGHTS

We ran a survey to identify researcher needs.

Here's what we found.

THE TOP TWO CLOUD SERVICE NEEDS WERE:

Access to
transport data

Advanced
search options

"If I have to work as hard to find and understand the data set as I would to create my own data, I'd rather create my own data."

Only **5%** shared data openly, **28%** shared under restrictions and **20%** shared on request.

3 CATEGORIES OF DATA FOR THE TRANSPORT RESEARCH CLOUD

Original (raw)
research data

e.g. Field Operational
Tests and Naturalistic
Driving Studies

Operational data
related to research

e.g. accident data,
transport
volumes data

Data evidencing
published research

Report and recommendations from the

EXPERT GROUP ON OPEN SCIENCE TRANSPORT RESEARCH CLOUD

J. Rod Franklin, Kühne Logistics University (Chair)
Katarzyna Nowicka, Warsaw School of Economics
(Rapporteur)

Martin Böhm, AustriaTech

Sarah Jones, Digital Curation Centre

Tatiana Kovacikova, University of Zilina

George Yannis, National Technical University of Athens

Many thanks to all who responded to the survey and in particular to the European Commission who commissioned and oversaw the work.

Practical information

FIND OUT MORE AT:
<https://ec.europa.eu/research/transport>

FULL REPORT AND SURVEY DATA AT:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1469661>

The content of this leaflet does not reflect the official opinion of the European Commission. Responsibility for the information and views expressed in the leaflet lies entirely with the authors.

© European Union, 2018
Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.
Image(s): cover © Mimi Potter #122517225; p. 2 © bannosuke #126904353, 2018. Source: Fotolia.com.

European
Commission

Expert Group on Transport Research Cloud

*Addressing research domain
needs in the thematic pillars of
European Open Science Cloud*

Research and
Innovation

MANDATE

The Expert Group was commissioned in order to explore the feasibility and framework conditions for data sharing in transport research.

THE GROUP HAD A REMIT TO:

- Identify the main needs, obstacles and opportunities for data sharing & open science
- Identify the scope and the characteristics of data to be included in a possible Transport Research Cloud
- Identify data mining and analysis requirements and tools
- Identify a common set of cloud-based services
- Assess the relevance of the international dimension of a possible Transport Research Cloud
- Provide recommendations for different options of funding of a possible Transport Research Cloud

RECOMMENDATIONS

AGREE POLICY

- Make data Open and FAIR by default
- Ensure Intellectual Property management doesn't unnecessarily limit data sharing

DEFINE VALUE

- Ensure cloud services generate value
- Develop a sustainable business model

IMPLEMENT

- Define metadata standards for the discovery of transport research data
- Agree data formats and documentation to support understanding and reuse
- Incentivise researchers to share & reuse transport data
- Provide data mining and high-performance analysis tools to work with data at scale
- Offer secure data services for controlled sharing/restricted access
- Provide support and training to assist in culture change

ACTIONS

Bring together the research community and transport operators to co-design and agree data standards for the field.

Build on existing standards / specifications that have been adopted e.g. DCAT-AP.

Fund a Community Support Action to share best practice, build a network of expertise and generate a culture of Open and FAIR data in transport research.*

Develop a Code of Conduct for Transport Research Data that ensures data are shared and reused appropriately, safeguarding individual privacy and commercial interests while maximising the return on investment of public funds.*

* Actions to be funded under the European Commission's Horizon 2020, Smart, Green and Integrated Transport Work Programme 2018-2020.

Image CC-BY-SA by SangyaPundir
Source link: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:FAIR_data_principles.jpg